

Performance Characteristics of Water Yam Grater

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Abstract

This study presents an evaluation of a motorized tabletop water yam grater designed to address the inefficiencies and labor-intensive nature of traditional grating methods. The focus is on assessing the performance characteristics of the grater, particularly in terms of its grating rate and efficiency across different motor speeds. This study focuses on the design, construction, and performance testing of a mechanized abrasive water yam grater intended for household use. Using AUTODESK INVENTOR 2019, a model for a motorized grater was developed, featuring stainless steel components to enhance durability and efficiency. The grater was designed to operate at a rate of 80 kg/hr and was tested with 3 kg of water yam, achieving a grating time of 142.4 seconds per kg. The results indicate that the mechanized grater not only accelerates the grating process but also reduces labor intensity and minimizes the risk of injury associated with traditional hand-grating methods. This innovation seeks to address the evolving needs of yam processing by promoting safer, faster, and more efficient household-level water yam grating, while also encouraging the broader adoption of mechanized agricultural tools. The grater, modeled and fabricated using locally available materials, was tested at varying rotational speeds to determine its impact on grating time and the completeness of the grating process.

Keywords: *Water yam, Water yam grater, motor-operated Water yam grater, Abrasion on Obtruded Steel plate, Grating Capacity, Autodesk Inventor 2019.*

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Introduction

The water yam, also known as *Dioscorea alata*, is a tropical tuberous root vegetable with a rich history spanning thousands of years. It is among the numerous species of yam that have been grown for their edible tubers. Many ancient civilizations in Asia and the Pacific Islands cultivated water yams. Because of its nutritional content and climate flexibility, it was used as a staple food source.

Water yams are notorious for having a high-water content and being difficult to handle by hand Adeniyi et al., (2020). An analysis of the structure and genetics of local and commercial water yam (*Dioscorea alata*) variations is presented by Adeniyi et al, (2020). Many regions of the world use a lot of water yams, It is a widely consume tuber and it process is a labor-intensive procedure. Water

yam is traditionally grated by hand using graters or hand instruments like abrasion on obtruded steel plates, which can be laborious and physically demanding.

This method causes a lot of finger injuries to personnel involved in the operation. This traditional way of grating water yam is done by manually rubbing the peeled tubers against a roughened surface of galvanized mild steel on a wood or metal frame. Manual grating is tedious, time-consuming and usually results in injuries to the fingers of the operator. When grated, water yam can be used in the preparation of several dishes such as water yam balls, water yam portage, water yam pancake etc. Traditional grating results to non-uniform particle sizes as well as substantial losses arising from the inability of the person to hold small pieces of water yam during the rubbing process (Adetunji and Quadri, 2011). A number of equipment has been designed to replace traditional grating. The related works include mechanized grater, motorized grater, hammer mill, disk grater, and hand grater (Ajao et al., 2013).

Other designs have also been proposed like the improvised cassava grater Adetunji and Quadri, 2011 proposed a cassava scale grater for home use to treat the root vegetable hygienically. The cassava must be processed hygienically. This common food's commercial grating regions have circumstances that indicate sensitivity to food contamination. The design and construction of a cassava grater for household use have been enhanced. This research took into account machine effectiveness, safety considerations, and portability. The galvanized mild steel core of the drum and the grating hopper were updated, and the drum now has a stainless-steel sheet wrapped around it. The machine has a 1440 rpm, single phase, one horse power electric motor. The constructed grater had a production rate of 158 kg per hour and a price decrease of roughly 50%. Design and manufacture were enhanced for a cassava used at home. Consideration was given to machine effectiveness, safety considerations, and mobility (Adeleye et al, 2021)

The main goal of this research was to create a motorised cassava grating machine that is affordable for both middle-class and working-class individuals by using locally available materials in its design and construction. Creating a cassava grating machine that is easy to couple and decouple, has a hopper that conveniently holds a specific amount of peeled cassava without wasting any, a stainless steel grating unit to promote safe grating operation, and a sloppy delivery chute for easy discharge were the main objectives. A petrol engine or an electric motor can be used to mechanically or electrically power the device. The motorised cassava grating machine will significantly decrease the importation of similar equipment because it is strong, lightweight, and simple to use. The machine's portability allows for commercial production of cassava pulp, and it also addresses the issue of weariness brought on by human cassava grating. The powered cassava grating equipment performed admirably, according to testing.

Bello et al., (2020) recommended concentrating on problems related to power outages when creating a cassava grating apparatus. The gadget can be operated manually or electrically, depending on how it is constructed. There are two ways to operate the invented cassava grating device: electrical power and human power. It talks about problems with blackouts. Cassava is fed into the machine's main drum, which rotates at a steady pace, through a metal sheet-made hopper. The cassava is grated in this procedure to create cassava pulp. Due to its slant, the metal sheet chute that is manually controlled receives the pulp and delivers it out. The machine's efficiency was discovered to be 82.7%, while the electrically driven machine's efficiency was discovered to be 79.5%.

Ezeocha et al., (2012) Suggested a portable cassava grating device. A mobile cassava grating machine's output capacity was tested after it was conceived, built with materials obtained locally, and put to use. A mobile cassava grating machine's production capacity is evaluated once it has been designed, constructed with materials obtained locally, then tested again. The new design is superior to the previous iteration. It consists of a delivery tube, a grating drum, and a hopper unit.

It also includes tyres for basic mobility. All of these components are assembled on an angle bar frame. The machine drives a metallic cylinder that serves as the grater, and inside is a perforated plate that serves as the grating drum. The machine could produce 55.79 kg per hour..

Sharma et al., (2020) proposed a cassava grating machine as a solution to the issues of erratic power supplies, scarcity of petroleum products, and exorbitant prices of petroleum-based goods. the planning, building, and testing of a home-use pedal-powered cassava grater. Because most conventional graters run on electricity, they are reliant on the supply of electricity, which is currently unstable in Nigeria and often nonexistent in rural areas. This problem must be partially resolved by developing a technique that will make food processing easier for rural residents and improve their economic security because of the erratic power supply, limited availability, and high price of petroleum products. A pedal chain mechanism paired with an installed grater drum on a shaft is used to grate the cassava tubers.

Considering difficulties from manual grating and limitations from traditional method, this research was conducted to develop, fabricate and evaluate a water yam grater that would lessen and relieve the problems encountered from the use of hand-held tools such as abrasion on obtruded steel plate. This technology is also hoped to be more adoptable at home because of its less complex design, easier operation, and use of locally available materials.

Materials and Methods

Methodology

The studies were carried out using the conceptual framework shown in Figure 1. The water yam grater was designed to operate at different motor speeds, specifically focusing on the performance metrics of grating time and completeness of the grating. A 1.5-hp electric motor, set at varying speeds, powered the grater. Testing was conducted with 3 kg of peeled water yam, with each trial replicated three times to ensure accuracy.

Design Consideration

The design of the electric grating machine's component parts, the selection of materials for each part, an explanation of the system's operation, engineering drawings, the required system assembly, and the anticipated cost of manufacture were all addressed by the project's methodology. The electric motor, connection, grating drum, cover, bolt and nut, delivery chute, shaft, and ball bearing have all been found to require design. Additionally, the apparatus (Figure 1) consisted of five primary parts.

A black iron pipe was used to design the grating assembly in a cylindrical shape. A stainless steel sheet with holes made with 1-inch concrete nails was used to wrap it. The cylindrical container that held the water yam had a 2-inch offset and encased the grating assembly. The machine also included a stainless steel discharge outlet with a 60° slant and a trapezoidal hopper.

Sample Preparation

A total of fifteen kilogrammes of fresh water yam tubers were utilised in the assessment of machine performance. Samples were cut and peeled by hand, and then carefully cleaned. Each test trial's sample weight was three kilogrammes. There were three replications for every operational speed.

Figure 1. Front, Top and Side View of Motorised Water Yam Grater

Determination of Speed

1.5-hp electric motor with an average speed of 800 rpm was used for the water yam grater.

P_D = power used to drive the drum

P_D = weight of the grating drum x radius of the drum x speed of the drum

$$P_D = W_{gd} \times R_d \times W_d$$

N = number of revolution per minutes 800rev/min

$$W_d = \text{Angular velocity} = \frac{2\pi N}{60}$$

Shaft Diameter Selection

$$\frac{\tau_{xy}}{r} = \frac{T}{J} \quad (1)$$

Where τ_{xy} = shear force

τ_{xy} = Maximum shear stress

T = Torque on shaft

r = Radius of the shaft

$$J = \text{moment of inertia} = \frac{\pi r^4}{2} = \frac{\pi d^4}{32}$$

$$\tau_{max} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_x - \sigma_y}{2}\right)^2 + \tau_{xy}^2} \quad (2)$$

Performance Evaluation

The machine was designed to operate at a rate of 80kg/hr and was tested using 3kg of water yam. The test was carried out loading 3kg of water yam. The time taken to complete of kg was 142.4seconds. The capacity of the machine was determined as;

This is quotient of the cassava grated per time taken;

$$\text{Grating Rate} = \frac{\text{Weight of water yam grated (kg)}}{\text{Time Taken (s)}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Actual Capacity} = \frac{W_f}{T} \quad (4)$$

W_f = total weight recovered, kg

T = time it took to grate the water yam tubers, s

Performance Testing

Performance was evaluated by measuring the time required to grate 3 kg of water yam at different motor speeds. The grating process was observed for completeness, with attention to whether all the water yam was processed without significant residue.

Results and Discussion

AUTODESK INVENTOR 2019 was used to develop and model the machine. Isometric, orthogonal, and exploded views of the model water yam grater before machine production began. It was a manufactured machine. The device was put through several testing. The water yam tubers were collected from a farm, carefully cleaned, and then peeled by hand before being weighed. To stop cassava from being dispersed due to machine vibration, peeled water yam was fed into the machine through the hopper and kept against the drum using a piece of wood. The machine was run for a short while in order to allow the speed to settle. It was discovered how long it takes to grate a water yam.

Testing

Testing revealed that the grating time varied with changes in rotational speed. At lower speeds, the grating process was slower, but the completeness of grating improved as the speed increased. Conversely, higher speeds reduced grating time but occasionally resulted in incomplete grating. The optimal speed for balance between efficiency and completeness was identified.

Speed and Grating Time

The grater demonstrated varying efficiency levels across different rotational speeds. At 800 rpm, the time taken to process 3 kg of water yam was measured at 142.4 seconds. This speed provided a balance between grating time and completeness, making it suitable for household use.

Completeness of Grating

Full grating was observed consistently at moderate speeds, with minimal water yam remaining unprocessed. At higher speeds, there were occasional residues, suggesting that while time efficiency increased, some trade-offs in completeness were noted.

Conclusion

The motorized tabletop water yam grater successfully enhances grating efficiency compared to traditional methods. It offers significant improvements in processing time and reduces physical labor. The performance evaluation indicates that the optimal rotational speed balances efficiency with completeness, making the grater a valuable addition to household kitchens.

The grater achieved an impressive performance rate, effectively grating water yam with minimal residue. Its design and operation demonstrate a successful application of mechanization to a traditionally labor-intensive process.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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